

**MICROSCOPIC STUDIES ON TEMPERATURE-DEPENDENT FAILURE
PROCESS OF CONVENTIONAL AND TOUGHENED
CROSS-PLY LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

The temperature-dependent failure process of different cross-ply laminates, that is, (0/90₄/0), (0/90₈/0), and (0/90₁₂/0), was investigated for both conventional-type T300/3601 and toughened-type T800/3631 carbon/epoxy composite systems. Tensile tests were performed both at R.T. (20°C) and at 80°C. In-situ observation of failure process under uniaxial tensile loading was conducted by using a "tensile loading device" which was set on the stage of a scanning acoustic microscope (SAM). The important damage parameter, that is, the transverse crack density was measured as a function of applied stress using the replica technique. The temperature effects on the microscopic failure process and mechanism including first transverse cracking and multiple transverse cracking were discussed considering three dominant temperature-dependent factors that affect transverse cracking, that is, transverse crack constraint effect, thermal residual stress in 90° ply, and fiber-matrix interfacial bond strength. In addition, relationship between applied stress and transverse crack density was predicted by the distribution of transverse strength of unidirectional composites. It was found that large decrease in interface strength at 80°C affect the microscopic failure process.

KEYWORDS: Cross-Ply Laminates; Delamination; Microscopic Failure Process; Temperature Effect; Transverse Crack

1. INTRODUCTION

In many applications of fiber reinforced plastics, fibers are aligned in more than one direction

to provide high load-bearing capability. Among these composites, cross-ply laminates have been extensively studied because this is a basic laminate configuration[1-8]. The fracture process of cross-ply laminates under static loading is known to involve a sequential accumulation of damage in the form of matrix dominated cracking. One type of damage consists of multiple transverse cracks running parallel to fibers in 90° plies. Second type of damage consists of interlaminar delamination[9].

With the increasing use of CFRP for structural applications, it is necessary to study the behavior under various environmental conditions. For space applications, it is useful to study the mechanical behavior of these materials under different thermal environment. However, only few systematic studies of temperature effects on the fracture properties have been conducted. The fundamental microstructure mechanism is not yet clear or unknown despite of its significance.

In the present work, the effects of temperature on the fracture process and mechanisms of CFRP cross-ply laminates are investigated microscopically. In addition, relationship between applied laminate stress and transverse crack density was predicted considering the distribution of the transverse strength of unidirectional composite (UD).

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Three different cross-ply stacking sequences, that is, (0/90₄/0), (0/90₈/0), and (0/90₁₂/0) were used for both conventional-type T300/3601 and toughened-type T800/3631 composite systems. The specimen size was 100mm long, 3mm wide. Thickness of each ply is 0.125mm. Fiber volume fraction was about 60%. Materials properties are shown in Tab. 1. Both T300 and T800 are high strength carbon fibers, but the latter has higher modulus, strength, and failure strain. The 3601 is a TGDDM/DDS epoxy system, but the 3631 is a modified epoxy system for toughness improvement. GFRP tabs were glued on the specimen, which resulted in a specimen gage length of 30mm. Tensile tests were performed at R.T. (20°C) and at 80°C. In-situ observation of failure process was conducted using a scanning acoustic microscope (Olympus UH-3) with a "tensile loading device" on its stage. Transverse crack density was measured by replica technique. The distribution of tensile transverse strength of UD of each system was also obtained to discuss the fracture properties of 90° ply in cross-ply laminates.

Table 1. Materials Properties

T300/3601		T800/3631	
T300	$\sigma_B=3500\text{MPa}$ $E=230\text{GPa}$ $\epsilon_B=1.3\%$	T800	$\sigma_B=5600\text{MPa}$ $E=290\text{GPa}$ $\epsilon_B=1.9\%$
3601	TGDDM/DDS Epoxy Resin	3631	Toughened Epoxy Resin

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the temperature dependence of the tensile ultimate strength of cross-ply laminates. For both T800/3631 and T300/3601 systems, as the test temperature increases, tensile strength increases for (0/90₄/0), but decreases for (0/90₈/0) and (0/90₁₂/0). Temperature dependence of the ultimate strength of each cross-ply laminate is rather small because the ultimate strength mainly depends on the strength of 0° ply. However, temperature dependence of microscopic damage development process is very different as will be shown later.

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of ultimate tensile strength of CFRP cross-ply laminates (a) T800/3631 (b) T300/3601

Figure 2 shows the transverse crack density of T800/3631 system as a function of applied laminate stress. The transverse crack density is defined as the number of cracks per unit specimen length. As the test temperature increases, transverse crack density decreases. On the other hand, as shown in Fig. 3, as the test temperature increases, the transverse crack density increases in T300/3601 system.

Figure 2. Transverse crack density as a function of applied laminate stress comparison of experiment and theoretical prediction T800/3631 (a) (0/90₄/0) (b) (0/90₈/0) (c) (0/90₁₂/0)

Figure 3. Transverse crack density as a function of applied laminate stress comparison of experiment and theoretical prediction T300/3601 (a) (0/90₄/0) (b) (0/90₈/0) (c) (0/90₁₂/0)

Figure 4 shows the first cracking strain and transverse failure strain of UD. Figure 5 shows microscopic coalescence of fiber-matrix interfacial debonding at the tip of a transverse crack in T300/3601 (0/90₁₂/0) at 80°C observed by SAM (400MHz). Figure 6 shows a microcrack observed in 90° ply of T800/3631 (0/90₁₂/0) at 80°C. Figures 7 and 8 show SEM photographs of fracture surface of 90° ply of T300/3601 and T800/3631 systems, respectively. Figure 9 and 10 show 0°/90° interface of T300/3601 and T800/3631 observed by SAM (30MHz). Figure 11 and 12 show fractured specimen of T300/3601 and T800/3631 systems. Figure 13 shows sequential photographs of initiation of delamination in T800/3631 at R.T. observed by SAM (400MHz).

Figure 4. First cracking strain as a function of number of 90° plies and transverse failure strain of UD, experimental data and theoretical prediction (Bailey's)
 (a) T800/3631 (0/90n/0) (b) T300/3601 (0/90n/0)

Figure 5. Sequential photographs of coalescence of fiber-matrix interfacial debonding T300/3601 (0/90₁₂/0) 80°C (SAM, 400MHz)

Figure 6. Microcrack in 90° ply of T800/3631 (0/90₁₂/0) 80°C

Figure 7. SEM photographs of fracture surface of 90° ply of T300/3601 (0/90₁₂/0) laminate (a) R.T. (b) 80°C

Figure 8. SEM photographs of fracture surface of 90° ply of T800/3631 (0/90₁₂/0) laminate (a) R.T. (b) 80°C

Figure 9. 0°/90° interface of T300/3601 (0/90₁₂/0) R.T. (SAM, 30MHz)

Figure 10. 0°/90° interface of T800/3631 (0/90₁₂/0) R.T. (SAM, 30MHz)

Figure 11. Fractured specimen of T300/3601 (0/90₁₂/0) R.T.

Figure 12. Fractured specimen of T800/3631 (0/90₁₂/0) R.T.

stage 1

stage 2

stage 3

Figure 13. Sequential photographs of initiation of delamination, T800/3631 (0/90₁₂/0) R.T. (SAM, 400MHz)

4. DISCUSSION

Important factors to discuss the failure properties of cross-ply laminates are as follows: i) the first cracking in 90° ply, ii) transverse multiple cracking, iii) delamination at the tip of transverse crack, and iv) the ultimate failure. In this paper, i) first cracking and ii) multiple cracking are discussed.

4.1 first cracking Figure 4 shows the first cracking strain as the function of the number of 90° plies, and transverse failure strain of UD. The first cracking strains are larger than the transverse failure strain of UD for each laminate. This is the "constraint effect" that were discussed by Bailey et. al. In Fig. 4, predictions of first cracking strain are also shown which were calculated by Bailey's equation[3]

$$\epsilon_{\min} = \frac{2bE_1\gamma_t\phi^{0.5}}{(b+d)E_2E_c} - \epsilon_2^T \quad (1)$$

$$\phi = \frac{E_c G_t (b+d)}{E_1 E_2 b d^2} \quad (2) \quad \epsilon_2^T = \frac{\Delta T (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) E_1 b}{E_1 b + E_2 d} \quad (3)$$

where b and $2d$ are the thickness of 0° ply and 90° ply, E is Young's modulus, G_t is shear modulus of 90° ply, γ_t is fracture surface energy of 90° ply in the direction parallel to the fibers. ϵ_2^T is thermal residual strain in 90° ply. ΔT is the difference between testing and curing temperatures. α is thermal expansion coefficient. Subscripts 1, 2 and c denote 0°, 90°, and composite laminate, respectively.

The predictions by Bailey's equation are smaller than experimental results and they do not give good agreement with the experimentally-obtained dependence of first cracking strain on the number of 90° plies. However, in the view of the dependence on temperature, that is, the increase in "constraint effect" at higher temperature, the predictions show good agreement in T800/3631 system, but not in T300/3601 system. This is due to the interface effect which will be discussed later.

4.2 Multiple cracking There are three important factors that affect transverse cracking, that is, constraint effect, thermal residual strain in 90° ply, and fiber-matrix interfacial bond strength. Among these factors, constraint effect and thermal residual strain suppress transverse cracking as test temperature increases. In T800/3631 system, experimental results showed good agreement with these two effects. However, in T300/3601 system, interface strength must be considered as an effect that diminishes the above two effects. Namely, drop in interface strength in this temperature range is so large that it overrules the above two effects. This is assured by the observation of interfacial debonding, as shown in Fig. 5, at the tip of a transverse crack at 80°C which was not observed at R.T.. In T800/3631 system, as shown in Fig. 6, microcracks that did not run through the thickness of 90° ply were

observed at 80°C. In this system, interface strength does not decrease very much and improvement in toughness of the matrix suppresses the transverse cracking in this temperature range. Figures 7 and 8 show SEM photographs of the fracture surfaces of T300/3601 and T800/3631 systems, respectively. In T300/3601 system, less fiber-matrix adhesion remains at 80°C. This also assures the decrease in interface strength. In T800/3631 system, on the other hand, little difference between at R.T. and 80°C were observed. In this system, large drop in interface strength cannot be expected.

4.3 Theoretical prediction of transverse crack development Next, prediction of relationship between applied laminate stress and transverse crack density will be made by using the statistical parameters that were obtained by the tensile tests of UD in 90° direction. As shown in Fig. 14, tensile stress in 90° ply recovers as the distance from the crack surface increases. Therefore, 90° ply in cross-ply laminates can be considered as the chain of elements which can fail once up to the ultimate laminate failure[6-8]. The strength distribution of the elements can be assumed using the distribution of transverse strength of UD. Then, failure probability of the elements under a stress is known and the number of cracks can be calculated by multiplying the number of elements.

From shear lag analysis, tensile stress in 90° ply at the point x apart from the crack surface σ is

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \{ \exp(-\xi x) \} \quad \sigma_0: \text{tensile stress in } 90^\circ \text{ ply with no crack} \quad (4)$$

$$\xi = \left\{ \left(\frac{G}{d_0} \right) \left(\frac{1}{bE_1} + \frac{2}{dE_2} \right) \right\}^{0.5} \quad (5)$$

where G is matrix shear modulus and d_0 is the thickness of shear region. Twice of x which meets $\sigma/\sigma_0 = 0.9$ was determined as the element length l_0 . Transverse strength of UD (volume V_s) can be assumed to obey 3-parameter Weibull distribution. The probability distribution function is

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left\{ -V_s \left(\frac{\sigma - \gamma}{\delta} \right)^\beta \right\} \quad (6)$$

where β is shape parameter, γ is location parameter and δ is a parameter that corresponds to scale parameter. When β , γ , δ are assumed independent on volume, the strength distribution of the element (volume V_e) is expressed as

$$F_e(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left\{ -V_e \left(\frac{\sigma - \gamma}{\delta} \right)^\beta \right\} \quad (7)$$

The number of elements, n , in the specimen (length L) is $n = L/l_0$. When 90° ply stress is σ , the number of cracks c is given as

$$c = nF_e(\sigma) \quad (8)$$

therefore, crack density ρ is

$$\rho = c/L = F_e(\sigma)/l_0 \quad (9)$$

On the other hand, 90° ply stress σ is sum of thermal residual stress σ^T and mechanical stress σ^M .

$$\sigma = \sigma^T + \sigma^M \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma^T = \frac{\Delta T(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)E_1E_2b}{E_1b + E_2d} \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma^M = E_2\sigma_a/E_c \quad (12)$$

where σ_a is applied laminate stress. Eventually, relationship between applied laminate stress σ_a and transverse crack density ρ is obtained as follows.

$$\rho = \frac{1}{l_0} [1 - \exp\{-V_c((\frac{E_2\sigma_a/E_c + \sigma^T - \gamma}{\delta})^\beta)\}] \quad (13)$$

Figures 2 and 3 show comparison of theoretical prediction by (13) and experimental results for T800/3631 and T300/3601 systems. The predictions show good agreement with experimental data in the sense that transverse crack density decreases at 80°C in T800/3631 system, but increases at 80°C in T300/3601 system. And the difference between predicted and experimental results is larger in T300/3601 system, which may be due to ambiguity in evaluation of thermal stress.

Figure 14. Analytical model

4.4 SAM observations Next, some observations of delamination and fiber breaks will be shown. In T300/3601 system, few delamination is observed. However, as shown in Fig. 5 (SAM 400MHz), microscopic coalescence of fiber-matrix interfacial debonding at the tip of a transverse crack is observed. Figure 9 shows 0°/90° interface observed from the front surface of the specimen by SAM (30MHz). A transverse crack running through the width of the specimen is observed, but not delamination. As shown in Fig. 11, fractured specimen showed flat fracture surface. On the other hand, delamination grows extensively in T800/3631 system. Figure 13 shows sequential photographs of initiation of delamination observed by SAM (400MHz). Increase in COD due to increase in applied load is observed (stage 2). At stage 3, fiber breakages in 0° ply and decrease in COD are observed. Figure 10 shows 0°/90° interface observed from the front surface of the specimen by SAM (30MHz).

Delamination initiated at the tip of a transverse crack is observed. And as shown in Fig. 12, the fractured specimen showed largely delaminated fracture surface.

5. CONCLUSIONS

(1) 90°ply in cross-ply laminates have larger failure strain than transverse failure strain of UD. This constraint effect is different in different material systems and in different temperatures. For T300/3601 system, large decrease in interface strength due to temperature rise diminishes constraint effect. For T800/3631 system, improvement in matrix toughness at higher temperature increases constraint effect.

(2) The difference of multiple cracking behavior due to material systems and temperatures can be predicted using transverse strength distribution of UD considering thermal residual stress.

(3) Microscopic failure process of cross-ply laminates is observed by SAM. It is assured that large decrease in interface strength due to temperature rise can affect microscopic damage development through the observation using SAM and SEM.

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